

////////////////////////////////////

DEVELOPING A REPRODUCTIVE HEALTH CARE DECISION AID FOR WOMEN AGES 18-25 AND THEIR MEDICAL PROVIDERS.

Debra Satterfield, Sunghyun Kang, Paul Bruski, Fred Malven, Andrea Quam* and Nora Ladjahasan**

* Iowa State University, Department of Art and Design, USA,

** Iowa State University, Institute for Design Research and Outreach, USA

*debra815@iastate.edu, shrkang@iastate.edu, bruski@iastate.edu, malven@iastate.edu, aquam@iastate.edu, nading@iastate.edu

ABSTRACT

Making a decision about reproductive health care is complicated for anyone. But for young women ages 18-25 that are making healthcare decisions on their own for the first time without another adult, it can be especially difficult. However, through improved communication with medical providers there are ways to empower these patients in the medical decision-making process. This research is the first stage in a multi-phase process to identify an effective communication strategy to facilitate more productive discussions between young women and medical providers. Improving access to information in ways that better fit the lifestyles of young women impacts their healthcare communication. Through better communication, it is expected that young women will make better-informed choices. In addition to identifying the information needs of young women, this research will also examine the information needs of medical providers, thereby satisfying the needs of both constituent groups.

Keywords: Reproductive healthcare, young women, Decision-aids.

INTRODUCTION

Research shows that difficult medical decisions can be made easier through the use of decision-making tools. According to the Cochrane Collaboration review, *Decision Aids for People Facing Health Treatment or Screening Decisions*, the use of decision aids compared to usual healthcare measures help people feel more comfortable with their decisions. This is made evident, they say, through reduction in scores on decision conflict scales.

People who use decision aids generally feel more informed about treatment options and clearer about their decisions with regard to personal values (O'Connor, et al., 2003).

While there are many online resources that discuss reproductive health care options, the information often is not encouraging young women to engage in more productive conversations with their medical providers. In one example, a website, plannedparenthood.org, offers to find an effective birth control method for individuals through a 23 question survey. While the questions are well designed, sometimes they do not provide an adequate solution due to the complex nature of the information provided by the participant.

If no suitable information is available for these young women, they may be more influenced by peers or advertising than by their medical providers. This situation leaves out an important piece of the decision-making process that should come from the clinical encounter between medical providers and patients.

The objective of this research is to identify an effective communication strategy to help young women better communicate with medical providers. Through better communication it is expected that young women will make better choices that better fit their life style and reproductive healthcare needs. In addition to identifying the needs of young women, this research will also examine the information needs of medical providers. This is done to identify the best way to provide accurate information through the context of a productive discussion between the

young women and their medical providers. It also assures that the information is delivered in a way that facilitates communication with medical providers and adheres to information privacy policies.

METHODS

Three different types of research methods were conducted to identify the needs and perceptions of young women and medical providers. These areas included:

1. Examining and categorizing existing websites and existing print materials;
2. Conducting two focus group studies; and
3. Conducting ethnographic observations of the clinical encounter between patients and medical providers.

STUDY DESIGN FOR DATA COLLECTION

Existing websites and print materials were analyzed with regard to their use of verbal content, visual images, information graphics, and color. Thirty websites that contained birth control information were collected through a Google search during September and October 2009. In addition, twelve examples of printed materials related to birth control were also collected from various hospitals and organizations in Iowa during September and October 2009. These materials were analyzed to understand the information available about birth control and how it is targeted to young women with regard to the use of ethos and rhetoric.

Based on this information, a series of questions were developed for two focus group surveys. One focus group study was conducted with young women ages 18-25 and a second study was conducted with medical providers. The female college student participants were recruited through flyers and word-of-mouth advertising and were required to be between the ages of 18-25. To enhance the quality of the information, the first recruited focus group participant was responsible for finding up to three additional group members. The additional members were to be people who were familiar with each other and comfortable talking about their views on birth control with each other. In the medical provider focus group, all members were medical providers

and all were employed by a university health care center.

To best facilitate the data collection process, it was determined that student/peer researchers were most effective at conducting the student focus groups. Therefore, four female undergraduate students were trained to facilitate the focus group studies. Each trained undergraduate student conducted a focus group study with 2-3 college women ages 18-25 during April 2010. A total of 9 women participated in the four student focus group studies. Nine survey questions were asked to identify these young women's perceptions and needs with regard to information about birth control methods.

Another focus group study was conducted with three medical doctors and one nurse practitioner during April 2010. It was determined that faculty researchers best facilitated the medical provider focus group. This group discussed nine questions that were parallel in nature to the questions in the student focus group survey. This focus group study was also conducted to identify the specific perceptions or needs of medical providers with regard to providing reproductive health care information to young women. It also collected information about how the medical providers perceived the needs of young women in seeking birth control information.

In addition, four clinical encounters between women ages 18-25 were observed. Because it was determined that the young women patients were more comfortable with non-peer observers, faculty members of the research team conducted these ethnographic observations. The clinical observations were done to examine the content and context of the communication between a patient and a medical provider. Only the interview phase of the clinical encounter was observed and the researchers left prior to any physical examinations. Prior to the clinical encounter, both patient and medical provider participants were given an informed consent document and information about the research objectives. To collect the data from the clinical encounter, the observer entered the room at the same time as the patient and medical provider.

The observer would sit in an unobtrusive area of the room and was encouraged to only answer basic questions with regard to their role as a researcher. The observer was instructed not to engage in any additional conversation or offer any comments that would impact the data collection process. Video and audio recording and note taking were not allowed during the observation to maintain the integrity of the encounter and to reduce the intrusiveness of the observer. These direct observations were used to understand the needs of both patient and the medical provider in the context of actual clinic visits. Immediately upon leaving the clinical encounter, the details of the clinical environment (lighting, sound, posters and informational materials), the physical proximities of the patient and medical provider (sitting, standing, reclining), and the content of the verbal and non-verbal communication exchanges were recorded in an observation matrix.

DATA COLLECTION AND FINDINGS

WEBSITE ANALYSIS

Thirty websites on birth control were analyzed to identify the types of content and visual elements that have been used to provide information about women’s health and birth control. The use of color was of particular interest with regard to its ability to create a sense of gender bias in the design. The dominant color and sub-dominant colors on these websites were categorized to identify the use of color for gender associations, navigation, style and emphasis. Black as a color when used for text was not considered to be of significance.

Among the 30 websites, the color blue was used the most on 15 websites and the color yellow was the second most used with 8 websites. Ten websites used blue as the dominant color. Six websites used the colors blue and yellow in combination. In these cases of combined blue and yellow, the blue was used for the navigation bar and yellow was used as a spot color to emphasize information (figure 1). Seven websites used purple in their color palette. Additionally, five websites used purple as the predominant color and three websites used pink as the predominant color. Green and gray were also

used in five websites. Many websites also used pastel colors to provide a warm and comfortable feeling (figure 2).

Figure 1. The WebMD website shows how soft blue and yellow are used for navigation and site identification.

Figure 2. The BirthControlBuzz.com shows how a soft pastel purple can be used with a dark purple to create a monochromatic palette.

Fifteen websites did not use any images at all, while five websites used female photo(s) and two websites showed both male and female photos. Six websites used simple graphics to show birth control methods. Two websites used leaves and fruit.

PRINT MATERIAL ANALYSIS

Out of twelve printed brochures, six used photos with a female in the image. These images are used in various ways such as a female patient with a female doctor, college students, career women, and a mother and child. Only two brochures showed graphics with medical supplies for birth control. Butterflies on a flower, rabbits, and wedding rings were also used. Red, blue, and green are the most used colors in the print materials. Purple and pink

were used in two brochures and yellow was used in three brochures. Fifty-eight percent of the brochures were tri-fold from a letter size paper and contained very limited information.

FOCUS GROUP STUDIES WITH YOUNG FEMALE PARTICIPANTS

The focus group participants indicated there were a variety of reasons for selecting a form of birth control. Forty-five percent of participants responded that the primary reason to take birth control was to prevent pregnancy. However, the same percent of participants indicated that the primary reason to take birth control was to prevent cramps and acne. Twenty-two percent of participants responded that it was to regulate menstrual cycles and one participant responded that it was to mitigate anemia. Side effects, cost, timing, effectiveness, and privacy were all mentioned as a response to the question, what is the biggest reason for selecting a form of birth control?

All focus groups indicated they had concerns with regard to side effects such as those that influence mood and behavior. This side effect was the most influential with regard to the decision about whether to use a particular birth control method. This was followed by concerns about dosing issues and cost.

The majority of participants reported that they did not know much about birth control methods. While only two participants indicated that they were knowledgeable about birth control methods. Of those participants using birth control, forty-four percent indicated that they were worried about what happen if they skipped a day or messed up their schedule, twenty-two percent indicated they were worried about the length of effectiveness, and twenty-two percent indicated that they did not know how to use the selected birth control method.

The majority of participants from all four focus group studies indicated that they trusted their doctor's recommendation because doctors are health care professionals. However, one third of participants mentioned that they perceived the doctors offered them limited options.

Two thirds of participants mentioned they thought a website would be a helpful resource and one third of the participants wanted to see it in an interactive form. Participants mentioned that graphs, charts, and visual comparisons with a variety of options would be helpful. Also one participant mentioned that advertizing these informational resources is important so that young women are aware of them. Another student mentioned that she prefers to just ask to a doctor.

FOCUS GROUP STUDY WITH MEDICAL PROVIDERS

What should women ask a doctor before making a birth control decision? Medical providers indicated that it is important for young women to know the relative effectiveness of the different birth control methods. They also pointed out that patients need to let doctors know how long they want to use the birth control method and if they are interested in using it for contraception. Cost was also mentioned as an important factor for this young female population.

Medical providers indicated that matching a patient's lifestyle with her birth control method is very critical. Cultural differences and differences in personality both affect the use of a birth control method. The best methods for a young woman are the ones that she can definitely use and incorporate into her lifestyle. Therefore, medical providers indicated that understanding the patient's lifestyle with regard to things such as remembering to take a pill everyday, her comfort with inserting something vaginally, her comfort with getting an injection, and her willingness to insert an IUD must be considered when making a decision about a birth control method.

Medical providers perceived young women to be highly influenced by friends and peers when making a decision about a birth control method. They also perceived TV advertising and magazines to have an affect on medical decision-making by young women. They reported that some times young women visit the clinic with a specific brand named birth control pill or method in mind. Medical providers also expressed concerns that misconceptions or misunderstanding about birth control methods that come from the mothers of these young women are

very hard to overcome. From their experience, medical providers identified two types of patients; one group who has already made a decision about birth control based on information from their friends or peers, and another group who is actively seeking the medical provider's opinion before making their final decision about a birth control method.

The medical providers indicated that health conditions and family health history will affect what birth control methods are actually an option for each patient. A personal or family history of blood clots, breast cancer, smoking, and migraines with auras all impact the types of birth control that can be safely used by an individual. By contrast, the medical providers noted that patients themselves were primarily concerned with weight gain rather than more serious conditions such as blood clots.

Half of the medical providers thought that interactive computer apps would be most effective as a strategy for providing birth control information for young women and the other half of the medical providers thought that print materials would be most effective for this target audience. All medical providers agreed that they did not want to send or receive communication or information through email with their patients because of privacy issues and time constraints.

OBSERVATIONS OF THE CLINICAL ENCOUNTER

Four clinical encounters were observed during the discussion phase of the appointment. The discussion time with patients varied from 20 minutes to 60 minutes. In all cases, patients were observed to be listening and the clinicians were observed to be explaining birth control information and asking questions about family health history and patient medical history. In some cases, a 3D model or a poster was used to explain the options and functions of birth control. Only one patient was observed taking notes. Of the four patients, three asked some questions, but all patients spent over 90% of their time listening rather than asking questions and discussing information. The patient and clinician observations provide a insightful thought on a their communication relationships. Three patients were perceived to be comfortable in the clinical

encounter; however, one patient seemed to be nervous.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The findings of the focus group surveys, the clinician and patient observations, and the review of existing reproductive healthcare material were informative in developing a comprehensive communication strategy for both young women and medical providers.

VISUAL ELEMENTS IN BIRTH CONTROL INFORMATION

Overall, websites used very soft pastel color palettes even though complimentary color palettes such as blue and yellow were also used. Purple and pink are also frequently used colors for existing birth control websites. Most websites focused on the verbal content rather than on the use of photographic images. By contrast, print material used more photographic images than websites. Also print materials used more visual metaphors such as flowers, rabbits, butterflies, etc. Print materials tended to use stronger color combinations compared to websites. In general, web design was found to be more sophisticated and informative than print materials.

FOCUS GROUP STUDIES AND OBSERVATIONS

According to Patient Preferences for Medical Decision Making research (Arora and McHorney, 2000), most patients prefer to leave medical decisions to their physicians. In addition, Arora and McHorney also found that younger and more educated people with less severe illnesses prefer to participate in their medical decision-making process. Our findings indicate that the majority of young women ages 18-25 who participated in this focus group study trusted their medical professionals and wanted to delegate medical decisions to their doctors when making decisions about birth control. In contrast, the medical providers who participated in this focus group study perceived that these young female patients are more influenced by peers, parents, or advertising than by their medical providers. This difference in perception of preferred decision-making methods is critical to effective communication in the clinical encounter. This also demonstrates the need for a medical decision-making communication strategy that allows both young women and their medical providers to better

understand each other and their respective roles in this birth control decision-making process.

The research methods used in this paper to develop decision aids for reproductive health care provide a holistic approach for understanding communication strategies used by patients and medical providers in the clinical encounter (figure 3).

Figure 3. Communication strategy research methodology.

This methodology considers the social and emotional aspects of both groups with regard to their information needs and their lifestyle considerations. It also takes into consideration the content and

context of the clinical encounter where all medical discussions will take place. This acknowledges the role of each participant as well as the role of the environment with regard to their impact on effective and productive communication.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research was supported by Bailey research career development award. This research is the second phase in a collaborative project on the design and evaluation of medical decision aids with the Knowledge Encounter Research (KER) Unit at The Mayo Clinic under the direction of Dr. Victor Montori and Maggie Breslin.

REFERENCES

Arora, N. K. and McHorney, C. A. Patient Preferences for Medical Decision Making: Who Really Wants to Participate?. *Medical Care* 2000, Volume 38, number 3, pp 335-341.

O'Connor, A.M., Bennett, C.L., Stacey, D., Barry M., Col N.F., Eden K.B., Entwistle, V.A., Fiset, V., Homes-Rovner, M., Khangura, S., Llewellyn-Thomas, H. and Rovner, D. Decision Aids for People Facing Health Treatment or Screening Decisions. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews* 2003, Issue 1. Art. No.: CD001431. DOI: 10.1002/14651858. CD001431. p 45.